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“MAKTUB”

Your dreams are far
But remember
Everything is written in the stars

It may not be now
As you have battled
For better tomorrow

Savor your pain and failures
As it prepares you
For something greater

Believe in what you can do
And what is meant for you
In a path you walk
Your destiny is where
You are meant to be